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Title: SOP to flush the inlet components (infusion line and needle insert placed in H-ESI spray insert) prior to and after calibration of Orbitrap Fusion equipped with EASY-Max Ion source.

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Prior to each removal or reinstallation, always wear a new pair of lint- and powder-free gloves.

Make a note about flushing the inlet components to the Logbook.

SW: Xcalibur 4.7.69.37, Thermo Scientific SII for Xcalibur 1.8.0.530, Orbitrap Fusion Tune 4.2.4321

To remove syringe from the holder

1. Turn Off the flow from the syringe pump using *Syringe OFF* icon in Orbitrap Fusion Tune Application.
2. In Tune window (Orbitrap Fusion Tune Application), place the MS to Standby Mode.
3. Remove the syringe from the syringe pump holder as follows:
 - a) Lift the syringe holder off of the syringe.
 - b) Press the pusher block's release button and slide the block to the left.
 - c) Remove the syringe from the holder.
 - d) Carefully remove the syringe needle from the Teflon tube on the syringe adapter assembly.

To install the H-ESI spray insert with the calibration needle insert

1. In the Tune window, place the MS to Off Mode (Figure 1). After the API source cools to room temperature (about 20 mins) you can start to remove the current H-ESI spray insert.

Figure 1 Power mode icons showing the selected mode

2. For calibration the MS, there is a calibration needle insert already adjusted and placed in the H-ESI spray insert. This **HESI LoFlo Needle Insert 50 um ID35G (OPTON-30139)** is marked 'L' at the beige nozzle union (square PEEK ferrule).
3. Disconnect the red tubing of the beige nozzle union (square PEEK ferrule) from the current needle insert.
4. Unscrew the black locking nut of the current H-ESI spray insert, carefully remove it out of the API housing and store it having the probe covered by tubing with black cap in the box.
5. Pin-oriented place the H-ESI spray insert with calibration 'L' needle insert to the API housing, screw it by the black locking nut and reconnect the red tubing.
6. In Tune window, place the MS to Standby Mode and wait till the ion transfer tube temperature increases to 275°C.

To flush the inlet components

1. From the grounding union, unscrew the ferule connecting the divert valve and replace it via ferule connected through the infusion line to the syringe's needle (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Flushing the inlet components prior to and after calibration

2. Since **Pierce Flex Mix Calibration Solution (A39239)** is used for calibration, rinse the syringe with 50:50 acetonitrile/water solution at least five times.
3. Flush the infusion line and the calibration needle insert placed in the H-ESI spray insert at least once:
 - a) Load a 500 μl cleaned syringe with 50:50 acetonitrile/water solution.
 - b) Carefully reinsert the syringe needle into the Teflon tube.
 - c) Place the H-ESI spray insert to position 3 of the API housing to assure that flushing solution is leading into the waste tube.
 - d) In the Tune window, by *Syringe ON* icon turn on flow and change it 3 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ \rightarrow 45 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$. Prior to flushing volume runs out, change flow 45 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ \rightarrow 3 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ and by *Syringe OFF* icon turn it Off, Check that tubing connections do not leak during flushing procedure.
 - e) Following flushing, adjust the H-ESI spray insert to position 1 of the API housing.
4. The inlet components are now ready to calibrate the MS according to Calibration the MS procedure.
5. After successful calibration of the MS, flush the infusion line and the calibration needle insert in the same way as described.

Alternatively, to install the calibration needle insert into the H-ESI spray insert

1. Check the MS is placed in Standby Mode and disconnect the red tubing out of the beige nozzle union of the current needle insert.
2. Carefully replace the current needle insert by the calibration one as follows (see Figures 3-4):
 - a) With one hand, depress the needle insert's locking collar and loosen the nozzle union (square PEEK ferrule) of needle insert.
 - b) Slowly pull the needle insert out of the H-ESI spray insert and release locking collar.

Figure 3 Removing the needle insert out of the H-ESI spray insert

- c) Place the calibration needle insert into the H-ESI spray insert and secure it by rotating the square PEEK ferrule about four turns.
- d) Into the **Needle Adjustment Tool (PN80000-20957)**, place the H-ESI spray insert and make sure it is seated firmly.
- e) Press the locking collar and by rotating the square PEEK ferrule, adjust the calibration needle insert protruding the Tool to align its tip end with the edge of the Tool. The needle insert protrudes within 1.2 to 1.5 mm specification.

Figure 4 Adjusting the needle insert position by the Tool

- f) Place the H-ESI spray insert into the API housing, screw the black locking nut, reconnect the red tubing and continue by the section **“To flush the inlet components”**.

Note: The used figures were obtained from Orbitrap Tribrid Series (Thermo Fisher Scientific): Getting Stared Guide and Hardware Manual.